

STUDY INTEREST AND MENTORING ABILITY AS PREDICTORS OF STUDENTS' MATHEMATICAL FLUENCY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 6

Pages: 633-652

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2592

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14040944

Manuscript Accepted: 10-01-2024

Study Interest and Mentoring Ability as Predictors of Students' Mathematical Fluency

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Abstract

This research sought to examine whether study interest and mentoring ability have a significant impact on students' mathematical fluency. The study focused on selected private junior high schools in the municipalities of Monkayo, Montevista, and Compostela, where the respondents were drawn from. The statistical methods employed in this study included Mean, Pearson-r, and Regression Analysis. The research utilized a quantitative non-experimental design, specifically a correlation technique combined with regression analysis. Results revealed that the level of study interest in terms of feelings, value and involvement was high with an overall mean of 3.592 and has an SD of 0.66 reflected a descriptive rating of high. Furthermore, the mentoring ability was rated as high across several areas, including inspiring, managing risks, encouraging, providing corrective feedback, identifying goals and current reality, building trust, instructing/developing capabilities, opening doors, and listening actively which has an overall mean of 4.005 and has an SD of 0.584 indicating a descriptive rating of high. Additionally, the students displayed high levels of mathematical fluency in a variety of categories, including conceptual understanding, strategic competence, procedural fluency, productive disposition, and adaptive reasoning reflected to have an overall mean of 3.935, has an SD of 0.611. Additionally, the findings showed a significant and positive correlation between study interest and students' mathematical fluency which has an R-value of 0.699* and p-value of <.001. Lastly, findings revealed a significant and positive correlation between mentoring ability and students' mathematical fluency which has an R-value of 0.688* and p-value of <.001.

Keywords: *MAED-Teaching Mathematics, study interest, mentoring ability, quality education*

Introduction

One of the major concerns among students even before is the notion that Mathematics subject is an academic burden since it deals with numbers and they will engage in analytical and logical thinking and reasoning which lessens their interest in schooling (Wang, 2021; Panthi & Belbase, 2017). This pressing issue has deepened its depth since the pandemic as statistically reported by the American Indian and Alaska Native (AIAN, 2020) that student groups in 2020-21 resulted in low achievement compared to the previous school year. Relatively, a study among STEM students is expected to have less mathematical anxiety, this hinders the development of higher-level mathematical fluency, compared to social science students reversely result shows that mathematics is not one of the factors in choosing certain strand (Kraav et al., 2020).

In the Philippine setting, Mathematics is a learning area widely taught in primary and secondary education, where learners develop appropriate applied skills in problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, discussion, connection, expression, and decision-making to understand real life all-about. They are anticipated to grasp and value its principles as part of the fundamental K-12 education curriculum (Almerino et al., 2020). Eventually, the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) found that Filipino Grade 4 children performed lower in the international mathematics and science assessment than their classmates from other nations. The Philippines also received the lowest scores in both tests out of the 58 participating countries (Magsambol, 2020).

Moreover, mathematical fluency is the capacity of learners to recall mathematical concepts and facts automatically, as well as their number sense, flexibility of thought, appropriate and effective solutions to problems, accuracy of their answers, and comprehension of mathematical representations (Ankucic, 2019). Students who have strong mathematical fluency abilities may think more quickly, which gives them the drive, concentration, and focus needed to face challenging reasoning and problem-solving tasks. Additionally, reasoning-skilled problem solvers are required for the future. But when the emphasis in education changes to the analytical and imaginative side of math problems, we must not overlook the aptitudes and competencies that enable this way of thinking: mathematical fluency (Best, 2019).

Mathematics is considered to be an abstract subject, many students find it boring and perform poorly as a result (Yeh et al., 2019). Along with mathematics being abstract, students' lack of interest in the topic has also been attributed to their fear of learning it (Summer, 2020). Low accomplishment is caused by a lack of motivation in learning mathematics. One of the attitudes and determining factors that predict whether children will succeed in learning mathematics or avoid it is interest (Kihwele & Mkomwa, 2022). Studies have revealed a global trend of declining math proficiency (Mazana et al., 2020; Mbugua et al., 2012; Ndume et al., 2020; Sa'ad et al., 2014).

Relatively, mathematical fluency is crucial because it allows students to share their grasp of concepts, offers suggestions, and develops efficient problem-solving techniques. According to Cartwright (2018), fluency cannot simply be considered an achieved skill, as stated in a statement, "I'm fluent." Instead, it is a dynamic, ongoing process that continually develops. As teachers' expectations for mathematical fluency become more complex, the ability to maintain fluency and adaptability may temporarily plateau. However, this ability can progress to renewed comfort, where one can readily recall essential information and grasp the necessary steps to tackle more

challenging tasks.

The mathematical skills essential for everyday life, as noted by Stoessiger (2002), differ fundamentally from those taught in literacy classes. In mathematics, students must decipher and interpret a range of symbols, numbers, syntactical structures, and specialized vocabulary that form the basis of mathematical understanding (Ashby, 2009). According to Steen's (2007) article, *How Math Counts*, mathematics and numerical reasoning serve not just to produce answers but also to bring meaning to problems. Thus, mathematics is most effectively understood through the perspective of communication and interconnectedness. In mathematics, fluency is frequently associated with speed or the ability to recall information quickly (Ramos-Christian et al., 2008; Wong & Evans, 2007). Parish (2014) references Fosnot & Dolk (2001), who define fluency as the understanding of how a number can be composed and decomposed and the ability to apply this knowledge flexibly and efficiently in problem-solving.

This study is anchored to the study of Brown, Lent and Hackett in 1994 which is the Social Cognitive Career Theory and is commonly utilized in career development. Its goal is several aspects of career development, such as interest development, job options, and performance attainment. As to this theory, choices regarding one's career are influenced by both internal and external forces. More so, SCCT is derived from Bandura's general Social Cognitive Theory from 1986 which discusses environmental effects, behavioral impacts, and individual factors that are interdependent. Due to the three components' shared causality, they are always changing and dependent on one another. Finally, the researcher chose Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT) since it is relevant to the thesis topic. This relatively new idea has been widely used in comparable experiments, with compelling results. It gives a good foundation for comparing our findings to those of other researchers who adopted this approach.

Interest is widely recognized as a significant factor in learning mathematics (Heinze, Reiss, & Franziska, 2005; Yu & Singh, 2016). Gilbert (2016) demonstrated that students who exhibit a greater interest in mathematics tend to have lower performance-avoidance goals for mathematical tasks, regardless of whether those tasks require high or low levels of cognitive processing. An early interest in mathematics and a positive attitude toward the subject is linked with academic excellence and future aspirations in math and science fields (Luzzo et al., 1999; Strayhorn, 2015). Research indicates that students who demonstrate an early interest in mathematics and science are more likely to pursue mathematics-related courses and have aspirations for higher education in these disciplines (Strayhorn, 2015). Motivation and curiosity, according to researchers, may be required for academic performance and future job. As a result, student attitude and interest have become important educational notions since they are linked to student learning (Singh et al., 2002).

Moreover, the results of this study are consistent with the Interest-Driven Creator (IDC) hypothesis in mathematics education. Numerous researches have investigated ways to foster and increase students' enthusiasm in learning mathematics. According to the IDC hypothesis, students can develop their creative skills by consistently participating in activities that are led by their interests, particularly when technology is used to support these activities (Chan et al., 2018, as quoted by Roschelle & Burke, 2019). They added that the three main ideas of the theory—interest, invention, and habit—are developed through a series of educational exercises that lead to a cyclical process. It can be helpful to present a mathematical issue that tests students' prior knowledge in order to effectively spark their interest in learning mathematics. This should be followed by scaffolding to help students tackle problems successfully, and finally, by demonstrating the practical value of the content being learned.

Apparently, in many countries around the world, including Australia, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Canada, and the United States, mathematics coaching is employed to improve teacher instruction to boost student achievement (e.g., Campbell & Malkus, 2014). Many schools and districts implement this approach to facilitate teacher learning within classrooms or other instructional environments. This practice is further supported by evidence demonstrating the critical role that teachers play in enhancing students' academic performance (e.g., Kuijpers, Houtveen, & Wubbels, 2010). Coaching relies on a decade of study that shows on-the-job, "job-integrated" training is the most effective strategy to improve teaching abilities and student accomplishment.

Literacy coaching appears to be a highly effective method for enhancing student achievement. According to Richard (2003), coaching is supported by a decade of research indicating that "job-embedded" training conducted on-site is the most effective means of refining teaching skills and improving student outcomes. Peer tutoring relies on the tutor's academic expertise and the specific support they can offer to the tutee. Consequently, research on various peer tutoring methods and their application can help educators and students identify effective strategies for achieving positive classroom outcomes (Outhred & Chester, 2010).

The work of Vygotsky is well known. This framework provides a basis for understanding both mentoring and teaching. As cited by Wertsch and Stone (1985), Vygotsky argues that mentorship or teaching works best when it motivates and triggers maturing functions that originate in the zone of proximal development. He describes this zone as "the gap between the current level of development, as assessed through independent problem-solving, and the potential level of development, which is achieved through problem-solving with adult support or collaboration with more skilled peers" (1978, p. 86). Tharp and Gallimore (1988) build on Vygotsky's work by suggesting that teaching (or mentoring) involves supporting performance within the zone of proximal development. Mentoring is considered effective when support is provided precisely at the point in this zone where assistance is needed to enhance performance. They have recognized a comparable method of support, termed modeling, which involves providing behavior for others to imitate. Wertsch's work (1984) has further clarified the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) by highlighting key conceptual insights. One such insight is "situation definition," which refers to how a situation is perceived and interpreted.

In addition, a theory of action designed to explore the connection between mentoring and student learning was developed based on the premise that students faced challenges in succeeding in mathematics and demonstrated a lack of independence and persistence when addressing complex mathematical problems (University of Washington Center for Educational Leadership, 2014). Gilbert (2016) also found that students who displayed a higher interest in mathematics tended to have lower performance-avoidance goals, regardless of whether the mathematical tasks were of high or low cognitive complexity.

Furthermore, the first independent variable, study interest, is reinforced by Knekta, Rowland, and Eddy (2020), who highlighted the significance of understanding how students' interest develops and fluctuates. Research indicates that interest enhances both retention and recall, suggesting its substantial potential for positively impacting academic achievement. Additionally, the second independent variable, mentoring ability, asserts that successful mentoring involves more than intuitive understanding. According to research, effective mentors and mentees who build and maintain constructive mentoring relationships have distinct qualities that support learning and development (Jones, 2003).

In relation to this, the dependent variable of the study, mathematical fluency, is supported by Areej Barham (2020), who emphasizes that understanding the development of individual interests is crucial for enhancing student retention in mathematics as a subject. This supports the claim made by Renninger and Hidi (2016) that stronger feelings of positivity, an increased sense of the importance of the subject, and a greater desire to participate in activities linked to the interest are all signs of a well-established individual interest. Therefore, the external validity of the instrument can be demonstrated by this comparison. Over the past years, in the extant literature, a significant increase in study interest, mentoring ability, and mathematical fluency exists. However, there has been no research on those three concepts together with the purpose of how these two variables influence mathematical fluency. Thus, this part of this study presents the related literature on the influence of study interest and mentoring ability as predictors of mathematical fluency.

The first independent variable which is study interest defined as an indicator that includes positive feelings toward Mathematics as individuals' affective experiences; perceived personal value of Mathematics refers to personal significance; and, independent and voluntary re-engagement with mathematics-related content and activities is characterized by an individual's intrinsic motivation to revisit the material and their capacity to do so without the need for external prompting (Eddy et al., 2020). The second independent variable includes indicators namely Shared Core Skills, which denote fundamental competencies required for effective performance across various roles or disciplines, and Critical Skills for Mentors, which involve specific competencies aimed at assisting mentees in developing particular skills (Jones, 2003).

In contrast, the dependent variable encompasses indicators such as conceptual understanding, which refers to students' grasp of mathematical concepts, operations, and relationships; procedural fluency, which reflects students' ability to execute mathematical procedures with accuracy, appropriateness, efficiency, and flexibility; strategic competence, which encompasses a student's ability to devise, represent, and resolve mathematical problems; adaptive reasoning, which denotes a student's capacity for logical thinking, reflection, explanation, and justification; and productive disposition, which reflects a student's tendency to find meaning in mathematics, recognize its utility and value, and see themselves as proficient learners and practitioners of mathematics (Barham, 2020). It explores these topics in depth to further comprehend the impact of study interest and mentoring ability on achieving strong mathematical fluency.

Research Questions

The main objective of the underline study is to examine the influence of study interest and mentoring ability on mathematical fluency. Specifically, this study was conducted to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of study interest to mathematical fluency in terms of:
 - 1.1. feelings/emotion;
 - 1.2. value; and
 - 1.3. involvement.
2. To describe the level of mentoring ability to mathematical fluency in terms of:
 - 2.1. listening actively;
 - 2.2. building trust;
 - 2.3. encouraging;
 - 2.4. identifying goals and current reality;
 - 2.5. instructing/developing capabilities;
 - 2.6. inspiring;
 - 2.7. providing corrective feedback;
 - 2.8. managing risks; and
 - 2.9. opening doors.
3. To describe the level of mathematical fluency in terms of:
 - 3.1. conceptual understanding;
 - 3.2. procedural fluency;
 - 3.3. strategic competence;

- 3.4. adaptive reasoning; and
- 3.5. productive disposition.
4. To determine if there is a significant relationship between Study Interest and Mathematical Fluency.
5. To determine if there is a significant relationship between Mentoring Ability and Mathematical Fluency.
6. To determine which domain of Study Interest significantly predicts Mathematical Fluency.
7. To determine which domain of Mentoring Ability significantly predicts Mathematical Fluency.

Literature Review

Study Interest

Gilbert (2016) found that students with a stronger interest in mathematics demonstrated lower performance-avoidance goals in tasks that demanded both high and low levels of cognitive processing. Academic progress and college goals in the math and science professions are correlated with early interest in and attitude toward mathematics. According to the findings, students who show early interest in math and science are more likely to enroll in math-related courses and have college aspirations (Strayhorn, 2015; Luzzo et al., 1999).

Mathematical performance and interest in the subject matter are positively correlated, especially for students who perform poorly at first. This result is consistent with the research of Köller and Baumert (2001), which shows that when learning is driven by extrinsic variables, such as the desire for high grades or the need to avoid the consequences of performing poorly, the relationship between academic interest and mathematics achievement declines. They suggested that interest plays a more crucial role in influencing mathematics performance when instruction is less structured.

Low-achieving pupils are forced to learn knowledge passively due to a lack of time. Barr and Tagg (1995) argue that low-achieving youngsters need more opportunities to learn mathematics at their own speed. Almost all students in Taiwan have a low interest problem, which is usually accompanied by a lack of motivation (Krapp, 1999). Furthermore, most Taiwanese pupils have little interest in or confidence in mathematics (Lee, 2012).

Relatively, minority students are less interested in STEM subjects as well. Many students conclude early that STEM-related fields are either uninteresting, challenging, or unpleasant, leading to a lack of motivation to pursue careers in science and mathematics (President's Council, 2010). Low academic achievement among students is a matter of national concern. The National Mathematics Advisory Panel (2008) reported that students in the United States performed poorly on international mathematics assessments such as the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) and the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA).

Mentoring Ability

Mathematics coaching is employed globally to enhance teacher instruction to boost student achievement, including in countries such as Australia, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Canada, and the United States (e.g., Campbell & Malkus, 2014). This approach is utilized by numerous school districts and educational institutions to facilitate teacher development within classroom or instructional settings.

Research also supports the idea that teachers play a critical role in enhancing student achievement, with coaching relying on a decade of studies showing that training is the most effective method for improving teaching skills and student success (Kuijpers, Houtveen, & Wubbels, 2010).

Mathematical Fluency

Mastery of fundamental mathematical facts is crucial for teaching mathematics at the elementary level. However, it is concerning that, despite the efforts of primary grade teachers to instill these basic math facts, many students still fail to achieve mastery. Lin and Kubina (2005) as cited in Baker and Cuevas (2018) states that fluency exists when students solve math facts with speed and accuracy. It is an important skill in both educational field and real-life actions (Bringard, 2017). It happens when a student gains 6 understanding in both facts, concept and ability to put on knowledge in solving problem (National Council of Teachers in Mathematics, 2014).

Mathematical fluency is vital because it allows students to express their understanding of concepts, share ideas, and apply effective strategies to solve problems with ease. Cartwright (2018) emphasizes that fluency is a continuous, evolving, and expanding process, rather than a fixed skill that can simply be checked off as complete. As teachers' comprehension of mathematical fluency deepens, their capacity to sustain fluency and adaptability may stabilize before progressing further. Eventually, this development leads to a renewed familiarity with fundamental facts and an enhanced understanding of the processes needed to address more complex tasks.

Additionally, the National Center for Educational Statistics (NCES) found that 22% of adults have not developed the mathematical skills beyond an eighth-grade level necessary for success in many occupations (Geary, Hoard, Nugent & Bailey, 2013). Mathematical proficiency is essential for student success both in the classroom and in real-world contexts (Cozad & Riccomini, 2016). While mathematics has traditionally been viewed primarily as a content area, there is now a greater emphasis on it within the K-12 curriculum. As educational standards continue to rise, the pressure on both teachers and students is increasing (Porter, 2011).

Researchers have identified competencies that support talent development as a result of the emphasis on 21st-century skills (Bellini et al., 2019). Of them, proficiency in mathematics is essential for schooling. Mathematical competence the capacity to develop and use mathematical reasoning to solve issues in everyday contexts. It is considered vital for lifelong learning in all European countries, according to the European Recommendations for Learning. One essential mathematical talent is numeracy, which is the capacity and desire to utilize and apply mathematics in a variety of settings outside of the classroom. In order to teach numeracy effectively, relevant procedures and activities must be included in addition to information. The European Recommendations emphasize that mathematical competence includes applying different kinds of presentation such as formulas, models, constructs, graphs, and charts as well as using mathematical models of mind such logical and spatial thinking. Counting skills are widely acknowledged as essential to children's development of mathematical competency on a global scale. According to Clements and Sarama's research, which Adelson (2015) cites, early numerical skills lay the groundwork for later mathematics comprehension and application.

This work is beneficial to the worldwide body of knowledge for it addresses the questions about fluency in Mathematics, which has many factors that affect its competence. Through this research's findings, many students and another individual are more knowledgeable, and the literature more profound. All junior high school students are expected to be aware of how to be mathematically fluent, for it will affect its study. This study will help the community and humanity for it will serve as a guiding torch in promoting the true meaning of fluency.

Furthermore, this study is helpful to both students and teachers in both public and private institutions. This study identifies the strengths and weaknesses of the students in terms of their study interest in their quest for knowledge; and for teachers to identify which part of their ability in mentoring needs more improvement and put more attention into. Additionally, it is helpful for the parents and guardians of the students in a way that they can help in the studying of their children and extend their hands for the betterment of their children in the quest for knowledge. Finally, future researchers may use this study as a guide for their future research, which may aid them in recognizing and gaining more knowledge about the study interest and mentoring ability that are predictors of mathematical fluency.

Methodology

Research Design

The correlational method to be used in this study is a quantitative non-experimental research approach. Non-experimental research designs look at social phenomena without directly affecting the circumstances that the subjects go through. Additionally, there is no random selection of subjects for the various groups. As a result, there is little data to back up the cause-and-effect correlations. A correlational design explores the relationships between two or more variables. A positive correlation occurs when high values of one variable are associated with high values of another. For example, there is a positive relationship between students' academic achievement and self-esteem. Conversely, a negative correlation refers to a situation where high values of one variable are linked to low values of another. For instance, conflicts between teachers and students negatively affect students' sense of belonging to their school (Frey, 2018).

Respondents

The research respondents are the ones who are involved in the study. The respondents of this study are the Grade 10 students of five selected private secondary schools in Municipality of Monkayo, Montevista, and Compostela, Davao de Oro. Accordingly, there are 845 students enrolled in the school year 2023-2024 in the entire Municipality of Monkayo, Montevista, and Compostela in private secondary schools.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Schools</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>
School A	151	49
School B	167	54
School C	201	65
School D	170	54
School E	156	49
Total	845	271

Additionally, its exclusion are the parents, teachers, and DepEd Officials. Hence, this study focused on influence of study interest and mentoring ability to a students' mathematical fluency, it is appropriate that the respondents are students.

Furthermore, a stratified random sampling was employed in the selection of respondents of the study. With this method of sampling, the respondents were not selected individually from the entire population, instead the selection was done by sections. Moreover, Slovin's formula was employed to get the sample size of the respondents. Hence, the needed number of respondents had reached to 271 in number.

Furthermore, the respondents were given the freedom to withdraw from their participation anytime if they feel threatened, physically uncomfortable, emotionally disturbed, or any other similar feelings or conditions during the conduct of the study. Presented in Table 1 are the name of school with its corresponding number of population and its sample: School A, School B, School C, School D, and

School E. Thus, the total number of students involved in the study is 271.

Instrument

The researcher utilizes adapted and modified questionnaires specifically designed to address the study's focus on both the dependent and independent variables.

For the first independent variable, a 33-item scale developed by Rowland, Knekta, and Eddy in 2020 for the BIQ or Biology Interest Questionnaire, is employed to assess individual interest, as outlined by Renninger and Hidi (2016). This instrument is designed to assess the study interest of Grade 10 students in learning Mathematics as a subject. The tool is a self-report survey that quantifies students' interest in Mathematics across three dimensions: (1) positive emotions towards Mathematics, consisting of 11 items; (2) perceived personal value of Mathematics, with 9 items; and (3) voluntary and independent reengagement in Mathematics-related activities and content, containing 13 items. Respondents indicate their level of agreement on a five-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally agree).

The adopted questionnaire was modified and simplified to fit the study perfectly. A panel of experts validated it. Testing of reliability and validity was conducted Olaycon Integrated School, Monkayo, province of Davao de Oro. The Cronbach's alpha was 0.801 and has a mean inter-item correlations of 0.168 which entails an internal consistency of good.

The second survey questionnaire is adopted from the article authored by Linda Phillips-Jones, Ph.D.'s entitled, 'Skills for Successful Mentoring: Competencies of Outstanding Mentors and Mentees' of which she provided a tool for self-assessment on this particular skill. This instrument consists of 14 Likert Scale items which will be rated as follows: 5 = excellent, 4 = Very Good, 3 = Good, 2 = Fair, and 1 = Poor.

The adopted questionnaire was modified and simplified to fit the study perfectly. A panel of experts validated it. Testing of reliability and validity was conducted Olaycon Integrated School, Monkayo, province of Davao de Oro. The Cronbach's alpha was 0.929 and has a mean inter-item correlations of 0.223 which entails an internal consistency of excellent.

The third survey questionnaire is originated and developed by Areej Barham (2020) and adapted for this study. These items were developed following NRC (2001) and NCTM (2000), which emphasize that teachers' pedagogical expertise in utilizing various mathematical representations and linking mathematical concepts are critical competencies for enhancing students' conceptual understanding. The 35 items were rated as follows: 5 = most relevant to my needs, 4 = relevant to my needs, 3 = fairly relevant to my needs, 2 = less relevant to my needs, 1 = not relevant to my needs.

The adopted questionnaire was modified and simplified to fit the study perfectly. A panel of experts validated it. Testing of reliability and validity was conducted Olaycon Integrated School, Monkayo, province of Davao de Oro. The Cronbach's alpha was 0.892 and has a mean inter-item correlations of 0.208 which entails an internal consistency of good.

Procedure

A questionnaire was used as the basis for the data collection process. The main goal was to establish a meaningful connection between study interest and mathematical fluency, as well as between mentoring ability and mathematical fluency and between study interest and mentoring ability.

In this research, the researcher investigated the significant relationship between study interest and mentoring ability in the mathematical fluency of the students. Thus, correlational design is appropriate to see the relationship between variables. Aside from that, the descriptive design is appropriate since it shows the level of learning interest, mentoring ability, and mathematical fluency of the students.

The following procedures were observed by the researcher to collect data for the study after the panelists' approval. The researcher obtained a letter from the dean of graduate studies authorizing and certifying the research, which serves as official documentation that UM Tagum College has approved the research. The researcher requested authorization to perform a study at various private junior high schools in Monkayo, Montevista, and Compostela, Province of Davao de Oro, from the offices of the school head/principal/administrator.

After acceptance, the letter of support was requested so that the researcher could provide the study's participants the survey questionnaire. The researcher also wrote a second letter to the teachers at the targeted private junior high schools to perform the study before distributing the survey to each group of students. Additionally, the researcher, who also described the tool's objectives, individually delivered the questionnaire. The researcher would also retrieve the questionnaire survey after the respondents have finished all the survey items.

The researcher tallied and tabulated all the data collected from the respondents after conducting statistical analysis. The statistical findings were scrutinized and interpreted. Using the data, conclusions were developed, and suggestions based on the study's findings were formulated. Additionally, the researcher ensured the protection and anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also secured consent from them. It safeguards the ethical standards of conducting research.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the conduct of the researcher's study, ethical issues and concerns may arise. It will ascertain that ethical standard would be strictly followed concerning protocol and standardized criteria, mainly managing the population and data such as, but not limited to the following:

Respect for Person. It guarantees that all respondents have the right to privacy to protect their autonomy, self-determination, and well-being. It emphasized the need for privacy of an individual about which information should not be known to others.

Voluntary Participation. All the respondents from the three private junior high schools were given the freedom to choose whether to participate or not in this endeavor without any effect or penalty. The researcher adheres to the human rights of the participants to contribute to the study voluntarily, without force or coercion.

Informed Consent Process. Respondents receive both an informed consent form and an assent form, providing comprehensive information about the research. These documents outline the research's advantages, privacy measures, procedures, and schedule. Respondents retain the right to withdraw from the study at any point. Both the researcher and respondents sign the consent forms. Prior to this, necessary approvals were obtained from the University's Research Ethics Committee, Graduate School Dean, School Principals/Heads, and teachers.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Respondents' confidentiality were safeguarded. Respondents' names remain undisclosed to ensure anonymity and privacy. This aspect were communicated during the researcher's orientation with the respondents. Data were collected, compiled, tabulated, and interpreted confidentially as the foundation of the study. It was stored and kept by the researcher with utmost confidentiality during the entire duration of the study. The researcher strictly adheres to the Data Privacy Law, ensuring utmost confidentiality.

Recruitment. This study involves Grade 10 students of a selected private junior high school in the Municipality of Monkayo, Montevista and Compostela. These students are currently studying Mathematics. Details about respondent distribution, data collection methods, questionnaire management, and participant involvement will be provided.

Risks. The study poses no significant risks to respondents' physical, physiological, or socioeconomic well-being. Respondents will receive briefing and debriefing sessions from the researcher through their advisor. Participating or not participating in the study will not affect their academic status.

Benefits. This study's findings hold benefits for selected schools in Monkayo, Montevista, and Compostela. It offers insights into the levels of study interests and mentoring ability for students' mathematical fluency. Respondents will receive certificates of appreciation and tangible tokens for their involvement.

Plagiarism. There was neither evidence to disprove the uniqueness of this corpus of research nor any indication that the author had plagiarized and passed off someone else's work as his own. Even plagiarism detected by programs like Turnitin and Grammarly was examined in the study.

Fabrication. The thesis asserts that purposeful misreading, intentional inclusion of false assumptions, and intentional use of inaccurate data have not altered the evidence presented here or its implications.

Falsification. The research did not misread works or manipulate data to fit personal biases. No change or exaggeration has occurred.

Conflict of Interest. The study is devoid of any conflicts of interest. No elements could compromise professional judgment due to secondary interests like monetary gain or academic rewards.

Deceit. As a result, the study finds no connection between respondents' gains and informational errors.

Permission from Organization/Location. Formal consent was sought from the hosting institution through a letter co-signed by the thesis advisor and graduate school dean. Ethical approval was obtained from the University's Ethics Review Committee. The research material will be submitted to the relevant agency. Necessary permissions will be sought from the school principals/heads where the study will take place. Following this, the researcher will request permission and guidance from the Grade 10 advisers of the sections where the respondents will be selected.

Authorship. The researcher, a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education-Mathematics, co-authored this study with Dr. Noel T. Casocot, the research adviser. The research underwent revisions based on the advisor's recommendations and adhered to the University's ethical guidelines. It also followed the processes set by UM Tagum College's Graduate School before, during, and after the study's conduct.

Results and Discussion

This section presents an overview of the outcomes and discoveries of the study. The outlined issues are presented in order. The variables examined in this study are study interest, the mentoring ability, and the students' mathematical fluency. Specifically, the researcher

aims to assess the level of study interest among students, mentoring ability among teachers, and students' mathematical fluency. Moreover, the researcher examines the significance of the relationship between study interest and students' mathematical fluency and the relationship between mentoring ability and students' mathematical fluency.

Level of Study Interest

The average mean score for study interest, assessed explicitly as high, is 3.592. Results show that the students study interest is oftentimes manifested. The data presents an overall mean, determined by averaging the responses to targeted questions from the questionnaire, which is provided in the appendix of this study.

Furthermore, the indications that achieve the highest scores were the focus on feelings with a mean of 3.927 and value which has a mean of that study interest is oftentimes manifested. Data shows that students place a significant emphasis on their emotions and value as part of their interest to study. The data presented an indicator involvement that exhibit a moderate level, as observed. The means score is 3.071 which indicates that study interest is sometimes observed.

Table 2. *Level of Study Interest*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Feeling	3.927	0.665	High
Value	3.776	0.71	High
Involvement	3.071	0.89	Moderate
Overall	3.592	0.66	High

According to the data presented in Table 2, the indication that ranks one of the highest among the three is the feelings. According to this indicator shown in Table 2, the highest mean is 4.376 which indicates a very high level, is observed that they enjoy learning Mathematics because they are interested to learn and followed by another mean score of 4.358 also indicating a very high level, which pertains to the acquiring new knowledge. Moreover, another four mean scores which exhibit similarly a high level as observed in Table 1.1. The mean scores of various proficiency areas are as follows: (3.734) which pertains to their happiness with learning topics and solving problems in Math; (3.753) means that they feel belong in the class that puts them in a good mood; (3.402) mean looking forward to getting back to class after a long weekend or vacation; (3.941) - they think that the field, Mathematics is very interesting.

Another ranking course is value, which obtained a mean score of 3.776 that indicates a high level. Data shown in Table 1.2 indicate the highest mean score is observed in the category of students believing that it is greatly and personally important for them to be knowledgeable, with a mean score of 4.292 indicating a very high level of proficiency, followed by students' learning they can gain from studying Mathematics which has a mean score of 4.162 a high level of proficiency. An additional various proficiency area that exhibits a similarly high level with a mean score of as follows: (3.635) indicating that students are confident that learning Mathematics directly corresponds to their personal preferences; (3.712) which indicates certainty that studying Mathematics has a positive influence on their personalities; (3.672) which pertains about studying Mathematics since it has a lot to do with the person I want to become. Lastly, students learning Mathematics since it is more important than the other things (e.g., hobbies, social life), indicating a mean score of 3.185 which indicated a moderate level of proficiency.

Lastly, the indicator that ranks third is involvement. According to Table 1.3, students talk outside the class about what they learned in Mathematics class has the highest mean of 3.262 which indicates a moderate level of proficiency; students engage more deeply with specific aspects of Mathematics, even when it is unrelated to any course requirements has a mean of 3.255 indicating a moderate level of experience. Next is students spent time thinking about topics in Mathematics voluntarily has a mean of 3.185 which is moderate. Also, the remaining five proficiency exhibit similarly with moderate level, as observed in Table 1.3. The mean are as follows: (3.111) which indicates that in their free time, students keep up with news stories related to mathematics through digital media platforms such as Twitter feeds, eBooks, online videos, podcasts, and blogs; (3.048) pertains to students visit mathematics-related exhibits such as zoos and mathematical/scientific museums as often as they can; (3.0) students engagement in Mathematics-related club; (2.856) indicates students browse through books or magazines with mathematical topics when they are in the library; lastly, (2.852) students attend mathematics-related seminars and presentations in their free time.

Level of Mentoring Ability

The average of teachers' mentoring ability is 4.005 indicating a high-level experience. The study's overall mean represents the average of the indicators linked to the particular questionnaire items about the studied variable. This suggests that the instructor's capacity for mentoring students is clearly and regularly displayed.

Additionally, as shown in Table 3 regarding mentoring ability, the highest mean was recorded for building trust, with a mean score of 4.143, indicating a high level of proficiency. The subsequent indicator, listening actively, had a mean value of 4.049, closely followed by instructing/developing capabilities at 4.048. Managing risks reached a mean of 4.041 while inspiring had a mean of 4.039. Providing corrective feedback followed with a mean score of 4. These variables obtained a very high classification among nine indicators of reasons for wanting to leave, a high score, which has a mean score of 4.054. Lastly, the data presented an additional three indicators that exhibit a similarly high-level proficiency, as observed. The mean scores of various proficiency areas are as follows: Identifying

Goals and Current Reality (3.988), Encouraging (3.868), and Opening Doors (3.867).

Table 3. *Level of Mentoring Ability*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Listening Actively	4.049	0.676	High
Building Trust	4.143	0.613	High
Encouraging	3.868	0.731	High
Identifying Goals and Current Reality	3.988	0.784	High
Instructing/Developing Capabilities	4.048	0.702	High
Inspiring	4.039	0.809	High
Providing Corrective Feedback	4	0.704	High
Managing Risks	4.041	0.732	High
Opening Doors	3.867	0.803	High
Overall	4.005	0.584	High

According to the data presented in Table 3, the indicator that exhibits the highest mean score of 4.143 is the building trust which has a high level of proficiency. According to the data presented in Table 2.2, the highest-rated factor is mentors respect boundaries, with a mean score of 4.387, indicating a very high level of proficiency and mentors admit errors and take responsibility in correcting it, which has a mean score of 4.314, which indicates a very high level. Mentors keep confidential things shared by us. with a mean score of 4.133, indicating a high level of proficiency. Additionally, mentor tells if and why I disagree or dissatisfied with something, so he/she knows that I am honest has a mean score of 4.092. The two remaining proficiency exhibits a similarly high level, as indicated in the table. The mean scores of mentors follow through on his/her promises is 4.007 and mentors spend appropriate time together with his/her mentee is 3.923.

The indicator of listening actively has the second-highest mean score of 4.049 with a high level of experience. According to the data presented in in Table 2.1, the highest-rated factor is appears authentically interested by giving encouraging responses like “That’s great...and Interesting...” which has a mean score of 4.162 indicating a high level, the mentor summarizes the key elements of what have been said has a mean of 4.144 indicating a high level of proficiency. Subsequently, the mentor uses appropriate nonverbal languages such as engaging in eye contact with people, nodding of the head, slightly leaning towards the students, smiling or frowning when appropriate obtained a mean score of 4.026. The last two competencies exhibit similarly with the same high level of proficiency. The following mean are as follows: (3.963) avoids interruption while talking each other and (3.952) mentors remember and shows interest in aforementioned experiences.

Instructing/developing capabilities, the fifth indicator has a mean score of 4.048 indicating a significantly high level of proficiency. Table 2.5 shows that mentor teaches me fresh knowledge, skills, and perspective by expanding concepts, giving great examples, and asking critical questions by a mean score of 4.406, which is significantly very high and mentor helps me monitor my performance and refocus my steps whenever needed has a mean score of 4.133 which is high level.

Moreover, the indicator that rank fourth is managing risks with a mean score of 4.041 indicating a high level according to the data presented in Table 2.8. All the items in this indicator exhibit a similarly high level of proficiency. The highest rated-rated item is the mentors help me identify the risks involved in projects an action, plus some mistakes I committed with a mean score of 4.155. Next is mentors make recommendations to help me avoid major judgment or action mistakes with a mean score of 4.144. Subsequently, mentors help me learn to prepare well and trust their own actions and decisions (4.114) and mentors provide suggestions to prevent further conflicts or issues (3.982). Lastly, the item that has the lowest mean score is mentors intervenes as their mentees’ advocate with others if requested in difficult situations with a mean score of 3.808.

Additionally, inspiring ranked fifth as presented in Table 2. The highest rated item pertains to the mentors inspire them to improve their weaknesses with a mean score of 4.295, indicating a very high level of proficiency. The remaining four items under in this indicator exhibit a similarly high level of proficiency. The following are their means and what it pertains, (4.07) mentors inspire them to take on challenges to rise above the average and do important things in their lives; (4.055) mentors help the students to observe other people who are inspirational; (3.97) mentors help them recognize inspiring actions that they implemented in the past and means to excel again; lastly, (3.804) mentors arrange other inspirational experiences for students.

According to the data presented in Table 2, the seventh indicator ranked sixth, providing corrective feedback with a mean score of 4.0, indicating a high level of proficiency. Mentors use positive words and tone of voice with them when their behaviors or products are not satisfactory has a mean score of 4.137, indicating a high level of proficiency and mentors offer actionable suggestions for the students to test next time scored 4.096 indicating a high level of optimism. Next is, mentors give specific feedback on behaviors with a mean score of 4.007 showing high level. The last two items under in this item exhibit a similarly high level of proficiency. The following as their mean and what it pertains: (3.985) mentors give the feedback as soon as possible after the performance; and (3.775) pertains to mentors gives corrective feedback in private.

In addition, identifying goals and current reality has a mean score of 3.988, indicating a high level of optimism. The highest-rated item is mentors set goals to achieve in my future career and personal life with a mean score of 4.022 indicating high level. Mentors recognize

areas in which students are able to perform well with a mean score of 4.004 which indicates a high level of proficiency. Next is, which has a mean score of 4 indicating a high level of proficiency is mentors knows what's important - what their students value and desire most. The data presented the last two items which has similarly a high level of optimism. The following are their means and what it pertains: (3.963) mentors accurately describe the reality of their capabilities and situations and (3.952) mentors identify particular weaknesses or improvement areas observed in themselves and ones seen by others.

Encouraging, ranked eighth among nine indicators, which has a mean score of 3.868 indicating a high level of proficiency. The highest-rated item is mentors' express thanks and appreciation has a mean score of 4.28 indicating a very high level of proficiency. The data presented has similarly high level of optimism. They are the following; (4.096) mentors compliment on students' accomplishments and actions; (4.077) mentors point out positive traits (such as perseverance and integrity) in addition to my performance and accomplishments; (3.476) mentors commend me in front of other people (being mindful of cultural differences and personal preferences related to public recognition and praise); lastly, (3.41) mentors praise them privately.

Opening doors, ranked last among nine indicators which has a mean of 3.867 indicating a high level of optimism. The top-rated item is that mentors advocate for students by speaking positively to individuals who could assist them in achieving their goals which has a mean score of 4.229 indicating a very high level. The remaining four items has almost with the same mean close to 3.7 – 3.8 which pertains to a high level of proficiency. The following are their mean and what it pertains: (3.819) mentors suggest other resources for me to pursue; (3.801) mentors personally introduce them to appropriate contacts; (3.782) mentors make certain my abilities are noticed by others and (3.705) mentors provide students with opportunities or assignments that allow them to engage with key customers, suppliers, and colleagues.

Level of Students' Mathematical Fluency

The responses on the level of mathematical fluency among the students at the five private schools that were chosen within the municipalities of Monkayo, Montevista, and Compostela are displayed in Table 3. It also draws attention to the differences found in every item for every indication used in the study. Students' overall mathematical fluency is high, with a mean of 3.935 and a standard deviation of 0.611. This suggests that there is a high display of kids' mathematical fluency. Additionally, a high degree of proficiency is indicated by the data, which shows that students' productive disposition received a total mean score of 3.96 with a standard deviation of 0.655.

The data includes the weighted averages and standard deviations of the four indicators of students' mathematical fluency. Additionally, the data provides descriptive counterparts for these variables. The mean score for adaptive reasoning is 3.954, while strategic competence has a mean score of 3.951, conceptual understanding has a score of 3.93 and procedural fluency has a weighted average of 3.879. All that has been mentioned above has similarly exhibit a high level of proficiency.

Table 4. *Level of Students' Mathematical Fluency*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Conceptual Understanding	3.93	0.663	High
Procedural Fluency	3.879	0.737	High
Strategic Competence	3.951	0.797	High
Adaptive Reasoning	3.954	0.785	High
Productive Disposition	3.96	0.655	High
Overall	3.935	0.611	High

The indicator with the highest value within the dependent variable category shown in Table 4 is productive disposition, with a mean score of 3.96 indicating a high level of proficiency. Students find Mathematics as worthwhile, useful, and sensible endeavor indicated a mean score of 4.155, high level as described, and Mathematics build positive attitudes has a high mean of 4.033. Students perceive learning Mathematics as an effort that pays off has a mean score of 3.974 indicating a high level. Additionally, Mathematics is set to enhance belief in one's own efficacy scored 3.93 indicating a high optimism level. Lastly, students have productive disposition in learning Mathematics for they are diligent has a mean score of 3.708 indicating a high level of proficiency.

The second indicator showing a high level of students' mathematical fluency is adaptive reasoning, as evidenced by a mean score of 3.954 indicating a high level. According to the data presented in Table 3.4, the items falling under this indication include Mathematics develop logical thinking with a mean score of 4.199 indicating a high level of satisfaction. Students can identify specific thinking skills in Mathematics has a mean score of 4.089 classified at a high level. In addition, students learn mathematical patterns has a weighted average of 5.963, a high level of optimism and students develop reasoning from specific information to make a broader generalization shows a mean of 3.959, a high level. Moreover, students develop reasoning from general ideas to specific conclusions shows a mean score of 3.919 indicating a high level of optimism. In addition, students enhance mathematical proof achieved a mean of 3.863, described as high level. The last two items exhibit closely a mean between 3.7 – 3.8 indicating a high level. These are the following: (3.86) students enhance skills in approximation, estimation, and prediction; and (3.779) students model problems in daily life situations.

The third rank among 5 indication is strategic competence which exhibits a mean score of 3.951, as shown in Table 3.3 indicating a high level of proficiency. The highest-rated items under in this indicator is students learn problem solving techniques (steps) having a

mean score of 4.022. The mean of students learn problem solving strategies is 4.018 which indicates a high level. Furthermore, the remaining three items has almost the same weighted average close to 3.8 – 3.9. These are the following: (3.985) students enhance skills in problem solving; (3.911) students develop ability in formulating word problems; and (3.815) students develop skills in representing worded problems.

The first indicator under this variable ranked fourth which is conceptual understanding, indicating a mean score of 3.93, a high level of proficiency as shown in Table 3. According to Table 3.1, the highest-rated item is students apply specific strategies for learning which has mean score of 4.137, a high level. Next is, students identify things that are included in the content exhibits a weighted average of 4.122, a high level of proficiency. Students learn via problem solving shows a mean of 3.915 indicating a high level of proficiency. Subsequently, students learn by using multiple mathematical representations has a mean score of 3.908, a high level of expectations. Students make connections between topics and procedures to reach generalizations has mean score of 3.897, a high level. The two items exhibit the same level of descriptive equivalence which has also the same weighted average of 3.886. These the following: (1) students amend alternative concepts and (2) students develop ability in forming connections. Lastly, with a mean score of 3.694, a high level is students use concept maps in learning.

The final indication is procedural fluency, with a mean score of 3.879, indicating a significantly high level. As seen in Table 3.2, the components encompassed within this indication. The mean score of students develop skills in learning appropriate procedures, is 4.018, indicating high. Students enhance skills in carrying out procedures accurately, gaining a mean score of 3.952, a high-level expectation. In addition, students learn mental operations and strategies reached a mean score of 3.875, which means high. The mean score is 3.863; students identify algorithms and skills, which is high. Students enhance procedural fluency in fundamental operations has a weighted average of 3.819 showing a high level. Lastly, students learn competencies in carrying out procedures flexibly in exercises with a mean score of 3.745, demonstrating high level.

Significant Relationship Between Study Interest and Students’ Mathematical Fluency

Test findings are shown in Table 5, which emphasizes the correlation between the factors investigated in the study and shows the relationship between students' mathematical fluency and their study interest.

The data shows a strong correlation between study interest and students’ mathematical fluency. These include feelings, value, and involvement, which have a substantial positive link, as indicated by the R-value of 0.695 and the p-value of <.001 indicating a significant positive association. The feelings has an R-value of 0.632 with a p-value of 0.001 which indicates a strong positive connection. Additionally, value has an R-value of 0.603 and with the p-value of <.001 indicating a strong positive connection. Lastly, the involvement indicator shows an R-value of 0.594 with a p-value of <.001, indicating a moderately positive correlation with the dependent variable, students' mathematical fluency.

Table 5. Significant Relationship Between Study Interest and Students’ Mathematical Fluency

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Dependent Variables</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>r2</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Feelings	Students’ Mathematical Fluency	0.632*	0.399424	< .001	Ho is Rejected.
Value		0.603*	0.363609	< .001	Ho is Rejected.
Involvement		0.594*	0.352836	< .001	Ho is Rejected.

The null hypothesis, which states that “there is no significant relationship between study interest and students’ mathematical fluency,” is rejected because the table shows that the indicators of Feelings, Value, and Involvement have the probability level of <.001 which is less than the level of significance at 0.05. The dependency between the variables, which ranges from moderate to strong, demonstrates three indicators, namely: feelings, value, and involvement.

Significant Relationship Between Mentoring Ability and Students’ Mathematical Fluency

Table 6 displays the nine (9) factors that demonstrate a substantial association between mentoring ability and students’ mathematical fluency. Identifying Goals and Current Reality has an R-value of 0.600 and a p-value of <0.001, indicating a significant positive association. Furthermore, Managing Risks has an R-value of 0.559 and a p-value of <0.001, implying a moderately positive association. Additionally, Instructing/Developing Capabilities shows a moderate positive connection with an R-value of 0.555 and a p-value of <0.001. Like this, there is a moderate positive association between Encouraging and the R- value of 0.541 with a p-value of <0.001. Next, Opening Doors has a high positive association with an R-value of 0.538 and a p-value of <0.001. Inspiring have a moderately positive connection with an R-value of 0.533 and a p-value of <0.001. Additionally, Providing Corrective Feedback have a moderately positive connection with an R-value of 0.520 and p-value of <.001. Listening Actively has a moderately positive relationship with an R-value of 0.511 and p-value of <.001. Lastly, Building Trust have a moderately positive association with an R-value of 0.478 and p-value of <.001.

The null hypothesis, stating that "there is no significant relationship between mentoring ability and students' mathematical fluency," is rejected as the table reveals that the variables inspiring, managing risks, encouraging, providing corrective feedback, building trust, identifying goals and current reality opening doors, instructing/developing capabilities, listening actively have a probability level of 0.001, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. This indicates a moderate to high correlation between the variables across

these nine indicators— inspiring, managing risks, encouraging, providing corrective feedback, identifying goals and current reality, building trust, instructing/developing capabilities, opening doors, and listening actively — have a significant impact on a students’ mathematical fluency.

Table 6. Significant Relationship Between Mentoring Ability and Students’ Mathematical Fluency

Indicators	Dependent Variables	r-value	r ²	p-value	Decision
Listening Actively	Students’ Mathematical Fluency	0.511*	0.261121	< .001	Ho is Rejected.
Building Trust		0.478*	0.228484	< .001	Ho is Rejected.
Encouraging		0.541*	0.292681	< .001	Ho is Rejected.
Identifying Goals and Current Reality		0.600*	0.36	< .001	Ho is Rejected.
Instructing/Developing Capabilities		0.555*	0.308025	< .001	Ho is Rejected.
Inspiring		0.533*	0.284089	< .001	Ho is Rejected.
Providing Corrective Feedback		0.520*	0.2704	< .001	Ho is Rejected.
Managing Risks		0.559*	0.312481	< .001	Ho is Rejected.
Opening Doors		0.538*	0.289444	< .001	Ho is Rejected.

Regression Analysis on the Domains of Study Interest that significantly predicts Students’ Mathematical Fluency

Table 7 shows an analysis of regression on the relationship between the dimensions of study interest and students’ mathematical fluency. The table shows an R-value of 0.699 and a p-value of <0.001, with an R² of 0.488 and a significance level of 0.01. The null hypothesis, according to which no domain effect of study interest substantially forecasts or predicts a students’ mathematical fluency, can be rejected. That is a domain of the impact of study interest that, as a result, strongly predicts or shapes students’ mathematical fluency.

The effect of study interest and students’ mathematical fluency are strongly positively correlated as shown in the Table 6 with an R-value of 0.699. The number of mathematical fluent students to 48.8% of the variance in the level of impact of study interest that students experience, according to the coefficient determination of 0.488. The remaining 51.20% is random fluctuation, indicating that other factors not examined in the study may also have an impact on the amount of effect of study interest.

The "feelings" indicator has a beta value of 0.328* and a p-value less than 0.001, both below the 0.05 significance level. This implies a substantial relationship between students' mathematical fluency and the "feelings" domain. In terms of domain comparison, "feelings" has the greatest beta, making it the most significant of the three. Furthermore, connected to "involvement" is a beta value of 0.266*, indicating significance at a level below 0.05. Lastly, value is associated with a beta of 0.204*, with a p-value of 0.002, lower than the significant value of 0.05. Thus, feelings, value and involvement have an impact towards students’ mathematical fluency

Table 7. Regression Analysis on the Domains of Study Interest that significantly predicts Students’ Mathematical Fluency

Indicators	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE				
(constant)	1.531	0.168				
Feelings	0.301	0.059	0.328*	5.111	< .001	Ho is Rejected
Value	0.175	0.057	0.204*	3.075	0.002	Ho is Rejected
Involvement	0.182	0.041	0.266*	4.476	< .001	Ho is Rejected

Dependent Variable: Students’ Mathematical Fluency R-value = 0.699* F-value = 84.817 R² = 0.488 p-value = < .001

Regression Analysis on the Domains of Mentoring Ability that significantly predicts Students’ Mathematical Fluency

Table 8 shows a regression analysis of the effects of mentoring ability to the students’ mathematical fluency. The table displays an R-value of 0.688, an R² of 0.473, and a p-value of <.001, with 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis, “There is no domain in mentoring ability that significantly predicts a students’ mathematical fluency” is rejected by the researcher. As a result, a domain in mentoring ability strongly predicts to the students’ mathematical fluency.

Mentoring ability and students’ mathematical fluency encounter a highly favorable outcome as indicated by the R-value of 0.688. According to the 0.473 coefficient of determination, students’ mathematical fluency may account for the 47.30% of the difference in the degree of mentoring ability of their teachers. Random fluctuation (52.70%) has an impact on mentoring ability.

The indicator "identifying goals and current reality" has a considerable influence because it is much below the 0.05 barrier, as evidenced by its less than 0.001 p-value and 0.282* beta. The impact of a mentor's abilities on students' mathematical fluency demonstrates the mentor's awareness of what is best for the students. In addition, the data demonstrate that additional domains generated larger beta values, demonstrating a more potent influence overall. According to the findings, some domains outscored others in terms of beta values. Furthermore, linked to "listening actively" is a beta of 0.169* and a p-value of 0.012, both of which are below the significance level of 0.05. This illustrates how mentors' ability to actively listen has a big influence on students' mathematical fluency.

Meanwhile, the beta values for opening doors, managing risks, instructing/developing capabilities, encouraging, building trust,

providing corrective feedback, and inspiring were 0.119, 0.113, 0.088, 0.058, 0.021, 0.014, and -0.014, respectively. Each indicator yielded p-values of 0.104, 0.138, 0.238, 0.420, 0.751, 0.845, and 0.868, all of which are slightly above the specified significance threshold of 0.05. Consequently, it can be concluded that mentoring ability does not have a significant impact on students' mathematical fluency.

Table 8. Regression Analysis on the Domains of Mentoring Ability that significantly predicts Students' Mathematical Fluency

Indicators	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE	Beta			
(constant)	1.118	0.208				
Listening Actively	0.153	0.060	0.169*	2.541	0.012	Ho is Rejected
Building Trust	0.021	0.067	0.021	0.318	0.751	Ho is not Rejected
Encouraging	0.048	0.060	0.058	0.807	0.420	Ho is not Rejected
Identifying Goals and Current Reality	0.219	0.054	0.282*	4.053	< .001	Ho is Rejected
Instructing/Developing Capabilities	0.076	0.065	0.088	1.182	0.238	Ho is not Rejected
Inspiring	-0.010	0.062	-0.014	-0.166	0.868	Ho is not Rejected
Providing Corrective Feedback	0.012	0.062	0.014	0.195	0.845	Ho is not Rejected
Managing Risks	0.095	0.064	0.113	1.490	0.138	Ho is not Rejected
Opening Doors	0.090	0.055	0.119	1.631	0.104	Ho is not Rejected

Dependent Variable: Students' Mathematical Fluency R-value = 0.688* F-value = 26.016 R² = 0.473 p-value = < .001

Level of Study Interest

Results indicated a high-level study interest focused on feelings and value while a moderate-level study interest in involvement. Students identified study interest in three key areas. Initiating interest in mathematics can enhance students' performance with lower achievement levels in an environment enriched with technology (Wong & Wong, 2019). This emphasizes how important it is to spark interest in students who perform poorly in mathematics because it is highly connected with improved mathematical outcomes.

Moreover, interest development is nonlinear, and more fluid than previously thought, with students pursuing multiple interests across multiple contexts, exhibiting differentiation and integration patterns over time (Akkerman & Bakker, 2018). It is important to ignite their interest in studying to succeed in their chosen path. Additionally, personalizing education through students' context active personalization, and choice can potentially increase individual interest in studying in a certain subject area as cited by Reber et al., (2018). It pointed out the possibility of increasing interest for students with low initial interest.

Students assess their learning experiences in terms of value, emotions, and involvement in detail. Individual interest is defined by Renninger and Hidi (2016) as having a greater propensity to participate in relevant activities, more pleasant emotions, and a heightened sense of value. This interest develops gradually as more information raises the relative importance and value of the material, which encourages continued participation and learning. Irrespective of the object's relationship to other objects, the related emotions and perceived worth are concentrated on that one object. For example, an individual who values mathematics primarily because it could lead to securing a prestigious job is experiencing extrinsic utility value, rather than deriving intrinsic value from the mathematics itself (Schiefele, 2009). Conversely, valuing mathematics because it is integral to one's self-concept and offers a fulfilling challenge would reflect intrinsic value.

In addition, higher interest and learning motivation positively correlate with student participation, with learning motivation having a more significant influence on participation as cited by Uyun et al., (2022). Students' involvement in the learning process affects their level of learning or competence. Additionally, Renninger and Hidi (2016) noted that as individual interest matures, the relationship between emotions, perceived value, and engagement becomes increasingly robust.

Level of Mentoring Ability

The previous chapter revealed that mentoring ability was high level. All indicators are reflected high: inspiring, managing risks, encouraging, providing corrective feedback, identifying goals and current reality, building trust, instructing/developing capabilities, opening doors, and listening actively.

Mentoring students can enhance their academic performance, social integration, and professional development, with benefits for both mentors and mentees Berinšterová (2021). Mentoring can be interpreted in various ways: as the transfer of societal values, skills, and norms; as an interaction between experienced and less-experienced individuals; or, more recently, as a learning partnership. A mentor facilitates the developmental growth of their mentee, who may be an adult or non-adult. This support can be provided through formal mentoring programs or through natural mentoring, where the mentor is someone within the mentee's social network. When effectively executed, mentoring leads to noticeable academic progress.

Students learn by how they are mentored by their teachers is affected by a high mentoring ability when it comes to listening actively. Effective mentoring to students involves providing feedback, listening, providing good examples, and offering problem-solving techniques as cited by Okoro (2018). Furthermore, according to Gottlieb, (2018), effective listening skills of the mentors lead to better

communication, increased productivity, and improved personal relationships. Active listening is the foundational skill in mentoring, upon which all other skills are built and depend. Effective listening shows both mentors and mentees that their concerns are acknowledged and understood. Moreover, students' learning about their teachers' mentoring ability is highly affected by building trust. Trust is a key factor in mentoring relationships; as it deepens, mentors and mentees become more committed to their partnerships, enhancing the overall effectiveness of the relationship. This trust is built gradually as mentors and mentees witness consistent and appropriate behavior. It is added by Kaplan (2019) who states that a strong mentoring relationship is characterized by trust, candor, responsiveness, time, emotional labor, and pushiness, which are crucial for academic success.

As reflected in the result, an indicator encouraging appears to be in high level. Phillips-Jones' research highlights that encouraging is the most esteemed skill in mentoring. This involves offering recognition and genuine positive feedback to mentoring partners. Furthermore, effective mentors foster their mentees' confidence through encouragement, facilitating their development. Humphrey (2021) defines mentoring as a relationship in which a more experienced individual provides support, direction, and incentive to help a learner achieve key life goals.

Furthermore, mentors' skills in identifying goals and current reality appear to be high. Philip-Jones asserts that both teachers and students must hold a well-defined individualized vision, clear goals, and clear understanding of their current realities. Mentors should engage in discussions with mentees about the mentees' aspirations, visions, and career or life objectives. Students are generally inclined to understand the mentor's insights regarding their strengths, limitations, and the organizational context, and they often seek guidance in identifying and understanding their own circumstances. Additionally, it is added by Bryson (2021) states that mentorship can support academic competence by providing emotional support, guidance, role modeling, and motivation, as well as assisting with career exploration, goal setting, and resource identification.

Mentors are likely to be proficient in instruction and growth. As Jones' research shows, this frequently does not include giving formal speeches or lectures. Instead, mentoring typically takes a more informal approach, such as exhibiting specific behaviors or sharing ideas and procedures in a one-on-one tutoring setting. Hilali et al., (2020) underlined that mentoring is critical for growing competencies and guaranteeing sustainability across many sectors; nevertheless, both mentors and mentees must understand their limitations and bounds to achieve effective outcomes. An essential aspect of effective instruction is to teach the mentoring process itself. This involves making process-related observations—identifying and pointing out specific mentoring strategies in use, and guiding mentees to understand the rationale behind these strategies (Jones, 2003).

Moreover, mentors' inspiring skills appear to be high. Exceptional mentors are distinguished by their capacity to inspire their mentees to greatness. Mentors can direct mentees toward future prospects that spark interest and drive by serving as a role model and exposing them to other great personalities and experiences—often exceeding their initial goals. The capacity to inspire varies among mentors. Humphrey (2021) describes mentoring as a relationship in which a more experienced individual offers support, encouragement, and guidance to assist a learner in reaching significant life objectives. A mentor provides coaching, listening, and advise and inspires their mentees.

Likewise, mentors' providing corrective feedback, according to the results reflect to be high. Along with offering regular and honest positive feedback, proficient teachers should also be ready to provide constructive feedback to their mentees. Teacher mentoring and learner beliefs about written corrective feedback enhance student performance in peer review tasks, with empathy and resonance being the primary advantages of peer feedback (Gao & Wang, 2022). Additionally, it is mentioned above that effective mentoring to students involves providing feedback, listening, providing good examples, and offering problem-solving techniques as cited by Okoro (2018).

Moreover, mentors' managing risks, as reflected in the result, appears to be high. According to Jones's research, mentors who want to effectively manage risk must be ready to shield their mentees from potential obstacles. Mentors have a major responsibility to steer mentees away from mistakes that may be avoided while also pushing them to take measured risks. The critical competency of "Building Trust" is closely related to this risk management skill. This process of risk management is often described as assisting mentees in venturing out on a limb and then soaring when prepared. Added by Boat et al., (2019) mentor personality traits, such as conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and emotionality, play a crucial role in how they perceive their capability to serve as a mentor.

Mentors typically can enhance the visibility of their mentees by creating opportunities for them to connect with influential individuals and showcase their abilities to various audiences. Studies indicate that when mentors provide this kind of endorsement, mentees' work is much more likely to be accepted. Furthermore, Bryson (2021) pointed out that mentoring is essential for professional growth since it provides direction, inspiration, emotional support, and role modeling in addition to helping with goal-setting, career exploration, and resource discovery.

Level of Students' Mathematical Fluency

Data show that students had a high level of mathematical fluency. The respondents gave a highly favorable considerations for conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning, and productive disposition. The result shows students who demonstrate these abilities have a beneficial impact on level of mathematical fluency. According to the findings of this study, students' interest to study and their teachers as mentors influence their mathematical fluency. The higher the level of their interest

to study, and how well they are mentored by their teachers, the higher the level of mathematical fluency; therefore, teachers and themselves influence mathematical fluency.

Teachers view mathematical fluency because of conceptual understanding, strategic competence, and adaptive reasoning, rather than just carrying out procedures (Cartwright, 2018). Additionally, Rahman et al., (2022) mentioned that higher mathematics anxiety negatively affects students' mathematical proficiency, while cognitive independence positively influences it. Thus, it is important to note that developing mathematical fluency at an early age plays a significant role to students' success in the future.

There is a high level of students' mathematical fluency in terms of conceptual understanding, as the data shows. This pertains to students' comprehension of mathematical concepts, operations, and relationships. The National Research Council (2001) and the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (2000) stress that for students to attain proficiency in this area, educators must possess both foundational knowledge and specialized instructional skills to effectively foster conceptual understanding. Shriki and Patkin (2016) highlights the importance of teachers facilitating students' ability to articulate their mathematical ideas. As a result, effective teaching includes the use of a number of representations, the ability to connect mathematical concepts, and the development of mathematical communication skills which are essential for developing students' conceptual comprehension.

Furthermore, students' mathematical fluency was high in terms of procedural fluency. This represents students' capacity to execute mathematical procedures with accuracy, appropriateness, efficiency, and flexibility (NRC, 2001). Educators should recognize that utilizing concrete models and engaging in practice drills are effective methods for aiding students in the development of mathematical algorithms and skills. It is added by Hendrickson et al., (2018) who states that in mathematics, procedural fluency can be improved through teaching practices that focus on student thinking, a learning cycle, and promoting procedural fluency through explicit instruction.

In addition, there was a high level of students' mathematical fluency in terms of strategic competence. This illustrates students' capacity to formulate, represent, and resolve mathematical problems. It requires that educators possess the necessary expertise to improve students' abilities in tackling challenges, such as word problems tied to particular mathematical concepts, and in cultivating effective problem-solving strategies and techniques (NRC, 2001). Additionally, teachers' ability to tackle multi-step fraction word problems is essential for developing effective strategies and accurately translating unknown values into mathematical solutions (Copur-Gencturk, 2021). This includes crafting suitable approaches, interpreting the problem mathematically by choosing the right strategies and representations to convert the problem into mathematical terms, and ultimately finding the correct answer.

Additionally, students exhibited a high level of mathematical fluency concerning adaptive reasoning. This reflects their ability to engage in logical thinking, reflection, explanation, and justification. Shriki and Patkin (2016) underscore the necessity for educators to have essential teaching skills to improve students' capacities for presenting mathematical arguments and justifications, advancing their reasoning abilities, and enhancing their reflective skills. Consequently, teachers should refine and diversify their instructional approaches, including performing mathematical proofs, making estimations and predictions, identifying analogical relationships that facilitate robust reasoning, and utilizing intuitive, inductive, and deductive reasoning methods.

Lastly, productive disposition appears to be in high level as indicator in students' mathematical fluency. This refers to the propensity to derive meaning from mathematics, recognize its value and utility, and perceive oneself as a capable learner and practitioner in the field (NRC, 2001). Additionally, productive dispositions in students help them engage in challenging mathematical problem-solving, with effort and thinking algebraically being crucial for successful problem-solving (Hoon, 2021). Educators should emphasize the significance of their abilities in fostering positive attitudes towards mathematics learning.

Significant Relationship between Study Interest and Students' Mathematical Fluency

The study revealed a substantial association between study interest and students' mathematical fluency. With a p-value less than 0.05, the computed R-value for each association suggested a positively strong link between the variables regarding feelings, and value. Involvement, on the other hand, are the only factor with a determined R-value that has a moderating positive association among the variables. The positive R-value showed a direct association between variables, implying that as the degree of study interest is high, so does students' mathematical fluency. Also, because there is a direct association between the two variables, it follows that as study interest improve, so does there is high level of students' mathematical fluency. Conversely, when study interest is low, so does students' mathematical fluency.

Results confirmed Ili (2021) conclusion that student learning interest in mathematics has a favorable and substantial relationship with their mathematics learning achievement. Numerous research studies indicate a strong correlation between the variable of interest and achievements in mathematics learning. Furthermore, if the students possess a high level of interest to study, the level of their competence in Mathematics will be evidently visible. Thus, students' interest to study is essential because it develops a high level of competence between students' mathematical fluency.

Moreover, good process skills and a strong interest in learning mathematics led to greater success in learning mathematics (Kamid, 2021). It must be noted that teachers should innovate creative ways in molding and igniting the interest of the students in class. According to Tambunan (2018), an important aspect in a teacher's influence on students' interest and motivation in mathematics

performance is effective communication of learning objectives and the construction of a comfortable learning environment, which account for 6.10% of the entire impact. Teachers are expected to serve as motivators by clearly communicating learning objectives and creating a welcoming learning environment, as well as using a variety of teaching approaches and keeping a pleasant classroom attitude.

Significant Relationship between Mentoring Ability and Students' Mathematical Fluency

The study revealed a substantial association between teachers' mentoring ability and students' mathematical fluency. With a p-value less than 0.05, the computed R-value for each association suggested a positively strong link between the variables regarding identifying goals and current reality. On the other hand, inspiring, providing corrective feedback, managing risks, opening doors, identifying goals and current reality, instructing/developing capabilities, listening actively, encouraging, building trust are the factors with a determined R-value that has a moderating positive association among the variables. The positive R-value indicated a clear association between the variables, implying that teacher's mentoring ability increases students' mathematical fluency. Furthermore, as teacher's mentoring ability is great, so does students' mathematical fluency. A students' mathematical fluency is low when teacher's mentoring ability is not great.

Data reveal the impact of teacher's mentoring ability to the level of students' mathematical fluency. Teachers' knowledge and capacity to mentor in an excellent way their students impact their level of competence in Mathematics. According to Carvalho (2023) mentioned that teaching mathematics in basic education through problem-solving helps students develop autonomous reasoning and interest, while promoting understanding and interest in the subject. Thus, it must be noted that teachers should extend their hands in teaching and mentoring their students by innovating strategies, and techniques that will enable the students to understand better the subject. Finally, it is crucial to acknowledge that mentoring proficiency plays a vital role in facilitating students' learning journeys and aiding them in becoming confident professionals (Tuomikoski, 2019).

Regression Analysis on Domains of Study Interest to Students' Mathematical Fluency

The study's dependent variable's regression analysis showed study interest domains significantly affect students' mathematical fluency. Results demonstrated that a students' study interest impacts their mathematical fluency. High interest to study has a beneficial effect on Mathematics fluency, which is a significant benefit. Study interest show a p-value of less than 0.01. According to the findings, all the domains had a considerable link with students' mathematical fluency – feeling, value, and involvement.

The research is based on the Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT) proposed by Lent, Brown, and Hackett, which establishes a connection between academic interest and students' proficiency in mathematics. As to this theory, choices regarding one's career are influenced by both internal and external forces. More so, SCCT is derived from Bandura's general Social Cognitive Theory from 1986 which discusses environmental effects, behavioral impacts, and individual factors are interdependent. Due to the three components' shared causality, they are always changing and dependent on one another. In addition, Ili (2019) mentioned that student learning interest in mathematics has a favorable and substantial relationship with their mathematics learning achievement.

Regression Analysis on Domains of Mentoring Ability to Students' Mathematical Fluency

Results show a regression study of the relationships between domains of teachers' mentoring ability and students' mathematical fluency. The students' mathematical fluency was affected by listening actively and identifying goals and current reality. However, listening actively, building trust, encouraging, inspiring, instructing/developing capabilities, managing risks, opening doors, providing corrective feedback have no discernible impact on a students' mathematical fluency in overall. Teachers' pedagogical competence, specifically general pedagogical knowledge, and classroom management expertise, significantly impacts students' mathematics achievement in lower secondary classrooms (König, 2021).

Additionally, teachers must have a strong personal vision, specified goals, and clear awareness of their circumstances. They should be open and honest with students regarding their hopes, dreams, and professional or life goals. Teachers can better help students in establishing and understanding their own goals by giving their perspectives on their own talents, limits, and organizational context. By sharing their insights into their strengths, limitations, and organizational context, teachers can better support students in identifying and understanding their own goals. The more teachers are aware of these components and can effectively communicate potential supports, the more likely they are to help students achieve their goals. Hidayat (2018) concluded that metacognition and achievement objectives improve students' mathematical modeling ability, with awareness, planning, cognitive strategy, and self-checking working as partial mediators.

Conclusions

The results indicated that two indicators of study interest among Grade 10 students, namely feelings and value, reached a high level of description. In contrast, involvement was assessed at a moderate level. Overall, study interest was observed among the Grade 10 students.

Students indicated high levels of conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning, and productive reasoning in the students' mathematical fluency, all of which were positively evaluated. The findings suggest a strong presence of students' mathematical fluency. The impact of mentoring ability and study interest on students' mathematical fluency

demonstrated a significant correlation with other variables and was notably strong. Additionally, the relationship between mentoring ability and students' mathematical fluency was moderate. However, when combined, both study interest and the teacher's mentoring ability exhibited a predictive effect on students' mathematical fluency.

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